

Linear vs Logarithmic Scaling for Ordering of Electrotactile Cues

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Abstract. Electrotactile feedback is versatile and research is mounting on how to practically use the modality. Most work investigating distinguishable parameter levels of electrotactile cues used linearly scaled levels, yet sensing often follows a logarithmic scale. In our work we directly compared linear and logarithmic scaling for electrotactile cues in an ordering task. Our results found that while correct ordering was slightly better with logarithmic scaling, this was not statistically significant. These results contribute to the discussion around how to best choose values for electrotactile cue presentation.¹

Keywords: Haptic · electrotactile · logarithmic scaling · linear scaling

1 Introduction

Electrotactile feedback is receiving more and more attention due to its versatility and flexibility. Research often focuses on exploration of the parameter space [3,7,1,4], subjective experiences [12,11,4] or practical application of the feedback [8,9,10]. When exploring distinguishable levels of electrotactile feedback, previous work usually used linear scaling [1,2,4]. While there is work arguing that haptic sensing might be logarithmic [5,6] according to Fechner's law, practical comparison of differences between linear and logarithmic scaling for electrotactile feedback is missing. In our previous work [4], we conducted a small pilot study to compare linear and logarithmic scaling for ordering of electrotactile cues, but the small number of participants did not allow for statistical analysis. Therefore, we extended the pilot to include 16 participants, which power analysis showed to be sufficient for statistical testing of small effects for our study design. Our results did show slightly better recognition rates for logarithmic scaling, but these turned out to not be statistically relevant. The majority of participants did not perceive a difference in the scaling type and those who did gave mixed feedback on which scaling they considered to be easier to order. Our work provides a first direct comparison of linear and logarithmic scaling for ordering of electrotactile cues and contributes to the discussion on how scaling type influences recognition of different levels of haptic feedback.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20286731>

2 Experimental Design

The experimental design was heavily aligned with and apparatus identical to our prior work [4]. The study was designed as a 3x2 within-subject experiment, with independent variables Parameter (Volume (related to Pulse Height), Pulse Width, and Frequency) and Scaling (Linear, and Logarithmic), and cues being presented on the non-dominant palm. All three parameters were first calibrated in the order: Volume, Pulse Width and Frequency. This entailed first finding the lowest value at which participants clearly felt the feedback and then increasing values until the cue became uncomfortable, involuntary muscle movement occurred, or, for Frequency, until no differences between calibration steps were felt. After calibration for each parameter, the three ordering cues for each scaling type were shown to the participant, ensuring that they could all be felt, were comfortable and clearly distinguishable. The three values were determined by choosing three equally distributed (rounded) values within the through calibration identified comfortable range for each participant, leading to the three values for linear (25%, 50%, 75%) and logarithmic scaling (19%, 41%, 68%). As the ordering task, all unordered cue sets (i.e.; without 1-2-3 and 3-2-1) for both scaling types and all three parameters were presented twice (48 ordering values overall), randomly ordered, and participants were asked to order the cues in each set from lowest to highest. The mean of correct ordering for each parameter/scaling combination was extracted for each participant. At the end of the experiment, a questionnaire collecting demographic data and ratings with the option for free text comment was presented. The ratings were presented on 5-point Likert scales for order difficulty, if they could feel all cues, and if they could distinguish the different parameters or scaling types, and which ones were easier to order if they did. Participants were sent the code of a £10 Love-to-shop voucher via email after the experiment. The study took around 40min and the University Ethic’s committee approved the study design. We recruited 16 participants (3 female, 13 male) between 25 and 46 (Mean=32.875; STDEV=6.60), all right handed, for the experiment, which a power analysis showed to be sufficient to show small effects for our experimental design with six conditions.

3 Results

The calibration varied between participants, with minimum values for Volume between 400-750 (Mean=581.25, STDEV=110.868) and maximum values for Volume between 650-1900 (Mean=984.375, STDEV=302.059). Minimum values for Pulse Width were between 100-350 (Mean: 218.75, STDEV: 83.417), maximum between 400-2200 (Mean=800, STDEV=417.931). For Frequency minimum values were between 1-2 (Mean=1.125, STDEV=0.342) and maximum between 15-44 (Mean=23.0625, STDEV=7.690). The number of correct ordering was consistently slightly higher for logarithmic than linear scaling ($V_{lin}=39\%$, $V_{log}=51\%$; $P_{lin}=42\%$, $P_{log}=47\%$; $F_{lin}=23\%$, $F_{log}=27\%$). We evaluated the ordering task with a repeated measures ANOVA using JASP, showing a significant

difference for Parameter ($F(2)=9.545$; $p<0.001$; $\eta^2=0.244$), but not for Scaling ($F(1)=3.359$; $p=0.087$; $\eta^2=0.035$) or the interaction ($F(2)=0.661$; $p=0.524$; $\eta^2=0.008$). Post hoc tests with Bonferroni corrections for Parameter showed significant differences between Frequency and both Volume ($t=3.821$, $p_{bonf}=0.002$, Cohen’s $D=1.048$) and Pulse Width ($t=3.746$, $p_{bonf}=0.002$, Cohen’s $D=1.027$), but not between the Volume and Pulse Width ($t=0.075$, $p_{bonf}=1.000$, Cohen’s $D=0.021$). Correct ordering for Frequency was consistently lower (Mean=0.25) than either Volume (Mean=0.449) and Pulse Width (Mean=0.445). 9 participants found the ordering task *Somewhat Easy*, 5 *Neither easy nor difficult*, and 1 each *Somewhat Difficult*, and *Extremely Difficult*. 12 participants could feel all cues (5 *Definitely yes*, 7 *Probably Yes*), 2 participants *Probably Not* and 1 each *May or May not*, and *Definitely Not*. 7 participants could distinguish the parameters during ordering (2 *Definitely yes*, 5 *Probably Yes*), where 5 each named Frequency and Volume were easiest to order, followed by Pulse Width (2). 8 participants reported they *May or May not* have been able to distinguish the parameters, while 1 participant thought *Probably Not*. When asked if they could distinguish the scaling type, 5 participants answered in the positive (2 *Definitely yes* and 3 *Probably Yes*), where 3 reported linear scaling as easiest to order and 2 logarithmic. 5 participants reported they *May or May not* have been able to distinguish the scaling type, while 2 answered *Definitely Not*.

4 Discussion and Conclusions

We compared the differences between linear and logarithmic scaling for ordering of electrotactile feedback. We found slightly better recognition rates for logarithmic scaling, as in our pilot study in our previous work [4], but these turned out to not be statistically relevant. Participant feedback also indicated that distinction between the scaling types was only possible for five participants, of which three found the linear scaling easier to order. Ordering is not an easy task as comparison between two pairs can be challenging and our previous work found that order of cues during the task can have an influence on recognition. We did not investigate these differences here, as we only wanted to compare the direct performance of the two scaling types. But, logarithmic scaling may have a bigger influence in an easier distinguishing task, which future work should investigate.

5 Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange.

Our work explores if different scaling between levels of electrotactile feedback can significantly improve ordering performance. It still remains an open question, whether our findings can translate to other use cases in which distinction of cues is necessary, but no ordering required, or multimodal settings.

Disclosure of Interests. The author has no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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